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Spectrophotometric Studies on Complex Formation of Tantalum(V) with 7-Nitro-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid

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THE colour reaction between tantalum(V) and 7-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid has been studied to determine the optimum condition for analytical use of this reagent.

Absorption spectra and the effect of pH :

Absorption spectra of the reagent alone and solutions containing tantalum(V) and the reagent 7-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (NHQSA) at different pH values exhibit maximum absorbance at 375 nm. The results obtained show that the pH range for maximum and constant absorbance is 6 to 7.

Beer's law and stability :

The Beer's law is obeyed within the 1 mg. to 5 mg. of tantalum(V) permillilitre range.

The formation constant K of 1 : 2 complex calculated by Job's method and Mole ratio method¹⁻⁵ is recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT OF TA(V)-NHQSA COMPLEX

Method	Log K
1. Mole ratio	8.03
2. Job's	7.93
Average = 7.98	

Estimation of tantalum(V) :

Several estimations of tantalum were made by the method described above. The average of five determinations with 3.50 mg. of tantalum(V) is 3.45 mg. which varies between 3.43 mg. and 3.51 mg. with 95% confidence limit.

Effect of diverse ions :

Synthetic solutions containing 10 ppm. of tantalum (V) and varying amounts of diverse ions were prepared at pH 6.5 and tantalum determined in their presence. The following ions, with amounts in ppm given in parentheses, did not cause more than $\pm 3\%$ difference in absorbance.

NO₃⁻ (350), Cl⁻ (15), Br⁻ (10), I⁻ (15), Thiocyanate (250), Oxalate (125), Ba⁺² (105), Al⁺³ (10), Tartarate (300), Fluoride (350), Mo(VI) (450), V(V) (375), W (400), U(VI) (425), and Nb(V) (500).

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Condensation of Acetylacetone with Aldehydes

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AN attempt was made to condense acetylacetone with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 5-bromo salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde. The main object of this investigation was to compare the reactivity of acetyl acetone with phenylacetic acid and its para halo substituted derivatives, in Knoevenagel's reaction. The condensation of phenylacetic acid and its *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo, *p*-iodo and *p*-fluoro derivatives has already been carried out in this laboratory¹⁻⁵. Another object of the investigation was to find out conditions in which maximum yields were obtained.

As the Knoevenagel's reaction involves carbanion addition to the carbonyl group of the aldehydes, any substance which yields a more stable carbanion will be more reactive. Phenylacetic acid as compared to acetylacetone is expected to give a more stable carbanion, because of the delocalisation of the negative charge over the benzene nucleus. Hence the yields obtained in the condensation of acetylacetone with different aldehydes should be lower than those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes under similar conditions. This has been confirmed by comparing the yields obtained in the present investigation (Table 1) with those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes^{2,3,6,7}.

Experimental

Condensation with benzaldehyde : Equimolecular amounts of acetylacetone and benzaldehyde were